

Integration of an Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) System in a Geothermal Power Plant

Dario Alfani¹, Paola Bombarda¹, Matteo D'Incalci¹, Elie Ghanatos², Ural Halacoglu³, Tugrul Hazar³, Feride İrem Eren³, Basile Chaudoir⁴, Titouan Janod⁴, Vincent Lemort⁴, Tristan Merbecks⁵, Mattia Piazza⁵

¹ Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

² CEA Grenoble, France

³ Zorlu Enerji, Istanbul, Türkiye

⁴ University of Liège, Thermodynamics Laboratory, Liège, Belgium

⁵ Turboden, Brescia, Italy

paola.bombarda@polimi.it

Keywords: storage, ORC, heat pump, flexibility, dispatchable power.

ABSTRACT

Geothermal energy, being available 24 hours a day, has traditionally been harnessed for baseload power generation. This approach has been economically viable given the high capital costs associated with geothermal power plants, as operating continuously at full capacity maximizes the return on investment. However, with the growing integration of intermittent renewable energy sources into the grid, the need for flexible and dispatchable power generation has become increasingly critical, and often more profitable than conventional baseload operation.

To achieve flexible power generation from geothermal plants it is possible either to enable flexible plant operation or to maintain baseload operation of the plant while coupling it with an ETES (Electro-Thermal Energy Storage) system to manage flexible power generation.

This paper focuses on the integration of an innovative ETES system developed under the EU-funded Project *SEHRENE - Store Electricity and Heat foR climatE Neutral Europe* in a geothermal plant. Thanks to the several technological innovations of this project, the ETES results in a highly efficient energy storage system that does not rely on critical raw materials. The paper provides an overview of the activities required to design and to successfully operate such a system.

The Kizildere II geothermal power plant, the largest Geothermal Power Plant (GPP) in Türkiye, operated by Zorlu Enerji in the electrical grid as a baseload power plant, is selected for this study.

This work examines key aspects of integrating the ETES system into the Kizildere II plant, specifically identifying the most suitable connecting points and discussing the potential of the ETES application.

The procedure developed in the context of the SEHRENE project for the ETES design and simulation is here adopted to broaden the analysis and investigate the maximum potential of the ETES application. After assessing the charge and discharge cycles, and evaluating the system round-trip efficiency, the influence of the ETES on the global performance of the geothermal plant is finally discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thanks to its continuous availability, geothermal energy has traditionally been deployed to supply baseload power. This operational strategy has been economically justified by the high upfront investment required for geothermal plants, as operating at full capacity maximizes the return on investment. However, the current shift towards renewable energy sources, particularly solar and wind, is reshaping the power generation sector: the intermittent nature of these sources necessitates their integration with flexible and dispatchable power generation systems and efficient energy storage solutions, to ensure grid stability and support Transmission System Operators (TSOs), enhancing both reliability and profitability.

As a result, flexible and dispatchable power generation has become increasingly critical, and often more profitable than conventional baseload operation.

There are several strategies to achieve flexible power generation from geothermal sources, including:

1. Enabling flexible operation of geothermal plants to supply dispatchable power.

2. Maintaining baseload operation of the geothermal plant while integrating an energy storage system to enable a flexible power output.

While several research activities deal with the first option (see for example (Altieri et al. 2016), (Irl et al. 2020)), this paper explores the second option, specifically focusing on the integration of an innovative Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) system in a geothermal plant, which is currently being investigated under the EU-funded Project SEHRENE.

The ETES system is aimed at absorbing surplus electrical energy when renewable production exceeds demand and requires waste heat as a further input: it is therefore particularly suited for geothermal plants as they generally feature both electricity production as well as the availability of waste or unexploited thermal power.

This paper provides an overview of the activities required to design and to successfully operate such a system. In addition to the definition of all the main ETES operating parameters, the size of the storage system must be selected: in the context of the SEHRENE project, an accurate feasibility study is performed, with reference to an intermediate size ETES system. On the other hand, in the context of this study the maximum potential of such ETES application, which corresponds to largest possible system size, is investigated. The selected case study focuses on the Kizildere II geothermal power plant, the largest Geothermal Power Plant (GPP) in Türkiye, operated by Zorlu Enerji.

1.1 Kizildere II geothermal plant: history and research activity

The Kizildere geothermal field is located on the northern flank of the Büyük Menderes Graben. It was the first geothermal field exploited in Turkey, and several plants have been built over the years (Kizildere I, Kizildere II and Kizildere III, for further details see for example (Alp Sahiller and Rougé 2021)). Kizildere II was designed as a combined heat and power (CHP) production facility, featuring 80 MW_e installed electricity capacity (60 MW_e from the flash unit and 2x10 MW_e from the binary units), 20 MW_t installed district heating capacity and 30 MW_t installed greenhouse heating capacity.

This geothermal power plant operates using a triple flash and binary combined cycle technology: a simplified plant scheme is reported in Figure 1. Due to depletion of the reservoir, the plant is currently providing about 50 MW_e and operates in the Turkey electrical grid as a baseload power plant.

Plant performance improvement, with the goal of increasing flexibility, is a key issue for this plant. The EU funded Geosmart project, run in 2019-2024 (<https://www.geosmartproject.eu/>) was focused on Kizildere plant; currently, two EU funded projects are investigating the possible technical solutions that can be adopted to improve Kizildere plant performance and flexibility: the first one is the SEHRENE project, which is the object of this paper, and the second one is the nGEL project (<https://www.ngel-geothermal.eu/>). In nGEL project, plant flexibility is the main goal, and the ambition is to convert the original plant into a trigeneration plant by providing heating, cooling and power according to the requirements of the grid, depending on the time of the day and season of the year. It will also target utilization of geothermal energy in frequency reserve market by an addition of a heat storage system with secondary ORC. In addition to these goals, nGEL will try to tackle the flexibility problem of the ORC power plants that has an ACC cooling system, where efficiency is dependent on the ambient temperature. An absorption chiller system will be utilized to reduce the thermal load on the ACC thus increasing overall efficiency of the ORC.

1.2 SEHRENE (Store Electricity and Heat for climatE Neutral Europe) project

The Horizon Europe SEHRENE project, started on 1st January 2024, investigates electro-thermal energy storage (ETES) through the development of an innovative Carnot Battery system.

During the charging phase, a heat pump is used to upgrade the temperature level of a waste heat stream exploiting renewable excess electricity, and to store it in a Thermal Energy Storage (TES) for later use. During the discharging phase, an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) exploits the stored heat to flexibly produce electricity and respond to load variations. The two thermodynamic cycles (heat pump and ORC) are coupled by means of an advanced TES featuring a single heat exchanger that utilizes a Phase Change Material (PCM) to achieve high energy density. To maximize heat transfer efficiency the employed PCM is embedded in a novel metallic Kelvin cells-like foam developed ad-hoc. The choice of constant-temperature thermal energy storage is particularly suited to this application as both the heat pump and the ORC cycles are characterized by a large share of heat introduction and rejection related to working fluid phase change.

These characteristics result in a storage system able to operate in a highly efficient and flexible manner, without dependence on critical raw materials.

Figure 2 Examples of ORC (left) and HP (right) cycles in T-s diagram adopted in a ETES system.

Figure 3. ETES configuration for the Kizildere geothermal plant. Point 8 and point 64 are the same as in the plant scheme; both HP and ORC cycles are recuperative.

3 ETES DEVELOPMENT

At the time of writing, several fundamental tasks are still ongoing; preliminary information will be therefore provided in the following paragraphs.

3.1 ETES design constraints

The ETES design requires to preliminary assess the system boundary conditions. The values of the properties for points represented in Figure 1 and Figure 3 are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Nominal values of properties for points represented in Figure 1 and Figure 3

#	T [°C]	P [bar]	\dot{m} [ton/h]	Fluid
1	178.1	10.65	2678.5	97% steam/brine
8	104.2	1.59	3088.6	100% steam/brine

58	50.6	3	283.9	99.9% steam/brine
64	24.1	3.63	9000	100% steam/brine

As already discussed, the geothermal fluid at point 8, prior to reinjection, is used to provide thermal power to the heat pump evaporator and constitutes therefore the waste heat input to the ETES.

The temperature of the Phase Change Material, which is essential for both HP/ORC cycle calculation, is preliminary selected following completed tasks in the SEHRENE project, and is set equal to 141°C. Four possible candidates have been selected as PCM in this temperature range, namely Glucose, $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2$ (56%–44%), $\text{KNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_3\text{-NaNO}_2$ (HITEC), Dimethyl terephthalate (DMT).

The cold source for the ORC condenser may be provided by the water flow from the cooling tower (point 64) or using ambient air. In the context of

SEHRENE project, water from the cooling tower is assumed as cold source, while, for investigating the maximum ETES potential, air condensation is assumed.

Besides these constraints, it is essential to specify the charging time and discharging time: the ETES system is designed to absorb excess electric energy during periods of surplus renewable generation, which is generally caused by photovoltaic (PV) technology, and thus may last several hours during the day. On the other hand, the system should be then able to release the energy during shorter peak demand periods (e.g., evening), when PV could not cover the load anymore.

Following completed tasks of the SEHRENE project, these assumptions were considered:

- discharging time: 2 hours
- charging time: 4 hours

For the ETES detailed design, the analysis must start from the brine mass flow at point 8: the thermal power extracted from the brine at the heat pump evaporator can be evaluated as

$$\dot{Q}_{HP, evap} = \dot{m}_{brine} c_{p, brine} \Delta T \quad [2]$$

where ΔT is the temperature difference between points 8 and 10 (Figure 3), representing the cooling of the brine: since the brine is highly mineralized, a minimum temperature of 85°C must be considered for point 10. It is worth to note that temperature at point 10 is an important design parameter: it is relevant for the performance and the size of the system. The adoption of a low value allows from one side to recover a large thermal power from the brine, but, on the other side, due to the resulting T-Q diagram at the heat pump evaporator, implies a reduction of the evaporation temperature and therefore a reduction of the heat pump COP and system RTE.

In the SEHRENE project, the focus is on the feasibility on an intermediate size storage system exploiting a limited cooling of the brine, and resulting in a high RTE; in the present work the focus is on the overall potential of the ETES application, therefore the largest possible size for the ETES system is considered.

In this last case it is assumed to use the whole brine mass flow for feeding the ETES and exploiting the maximum possible cooling of the brine; for the sake of safety, a value of 90°C is assumed for the reinjection temperature of point 10. Considering that the ETES will be designed as large size, it is likely that the water from the cooling tower will not be sufficient to reject to the environment the whole thermal power at the ORC condenser: this explains why dry air cooling is assumed for this study.

3.2 ETES design

Once the PCM temperature has been identified, the cycle working fluid must be selected. Besides common requirements, about environmental compliance,

toxicity, flammability and cost, the ETES working fluid must be selected considering the performance of both charging and discharging cycles, and component sizing, which strongly affect the techno-economic feasibility of these systems. A preliminary working fluid selection was tackled in (Cendoya et al. 2024), highlighting cyclopentane as the optimal working fluid.

Detailed design of the ETES components is currently ongoing; in the context of the ETES design, the sizing of the PCM heat exchanger is crucial, since this component is shared between the heat pump and the ORC. Due to the larger heat transfer duty associated to the discharging phase (shorter discharge duration), the ORC power cycle must be designed first, and the PCM heat exchanger is sized according to the discharge operating conditions: this implies off-design operation of the PCM heat exchanger during ETES charge phase.

With the final goal of developing a Digital Twin for the ETES operation, an accurate simulation model is being developed. To correctly evaluate the ETES performance, the simulation model should consider:

- the accurate value of the brine specific heat capacity
- the actual values of brine temperature and mass flow rate
- the detailed components design and geometry
- the actual values of temperature and mass flow rate for the cooling flow at ORC condenser

As far as the specific heat is concerned, an accurate model (GeoProp, see (Merbecks, 2025)) has been employed to estimate the specific heat of the brine with composition from Table 1: however, in this particular case, the specific heat value is not dramatically different from that of pure water, which can therefore for simplicity be adopted.

For the time being, the simulation model which is being developed is focusing on the actual off-design operation of the PCM heat exchanger; it is presented in (D’Incalci et al. 2025).

This model was at first employed to assess the preliminary selection of the working fluid with reference to the SEHRENE ETES: cyclopentane was confirmed as the best option among the considered working fluid candidates (cyclopentane, acetone, cyclohexane, isopentane, isohexane, n-pentane, R1233zd(E)) as it can properly balance the charge (HTHP COP) and discharge (ORC efficiency) performance, leading to the maximum RTE among the pool of investigated fluids.

3.3 SEHRENE ETES Performance

For the sake of completeness, prior to evaluate the maximum ETES potential, information about the current Sehrene project results are given. Aiming at an intermediate size storage system, it is here assumed to partially exploit the brine flow, considering a fraction of the whole mass flow (500 kg/s) and a limited cooling of the brine (ΔT about 3°C); moreover, water from the

cooling tower is considered for the ORC condenser. Main components assumptions are reported in Table 3 and

Table 4; a thermal efficiency of 95% has been considered for the TES.

Table 3 : Main assumptions for the design of the heat exchangers of the ETES system.

Heat exchanger	PCM	REC (low pressure)	REC (high pressure)	COND
ΔT_{pp} [°C]	5	8	8	5
ΔP [kPa]	50	8	50	8

Table 4 Main assumptions for turbomachine efficiencies

Component	Turbine	Pump	Compressor	Generator	Gearbox
η_{is}	0.85	0.75	0.80	0.95	0.97

Resulting preliminary performance is reported in Table 5.

Table 5 preliminary performance for the SEHRENE ETES system

ORC Cooling medium	P_{elHTHP} [MW _{el}]	E_{elabs} [MWh]	P_{elORC} [MW _{el}]	E_{elret} [MWh]	RTE [%]
Water	1.35	5.40	2.74	5.48	101.4

4 POTENTIAL FOR ETES APPLICATION

4.1 Geothermal plant performance

The current average Kizildere gross electric power is around 50 MW_e throughout the year.

4.2 Maximum ETES performance

The potential ETES performance calculation has been carried out with the model by D’Incalci et al. (2025) adopting cyclopentane as working fluid and assuming air-cooled condensation for the ORC; Table 3 and Table 4 still hold; an electric consumption of 1% of condenser thermal power has been considered for the condenser fan consumption. Table 6 contains the results of the conducted calculations; in case the values of the electric power/thermal power are too large to build the corresponding component with current technology, it would still be possible to consider smaller parallel units, achieving a similar overall effect.

Table 6 ETES maximum potential performance

$\dot{Q}_{evap,HP}$ [MW _{th}]	51.32	$\dot{Q}_{dischar,TES}$ [MW _{th}]	123.92
		$\dot{Q}_{pr,ORC}$ [MW _{th}]	34.00
P_{elHTHP} [MW _{el}]	15.09	P_{elORC} [MW _{el}]	24.99
COP_{HTHP}	4.32	η_{ORC} [%]	15.82
$\dot{Q}_{charge,TES}$ [MW _{th}]	65.23	$\dot{Q}_{cond,ORC}$ [MW _{th}]	130.81
$E_{th\ stored}$ [MWh]	260.91	$E_{th\ released}$ [MWh]	247.85
$E_{el\ absorbed}$ [MWh]	60.37	$E_{e\ released}$ [MWh]	49.97

5 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The analysis conducted demonstrates that integrating an ETES system into the Kizildere geothermal plant is not only feasible, but also presents significant technical and operational interest.

For the maximum ETES potential, with the considered discharge/charge durations (2 hours and 4 hours, respectively) preliminary calculations show that, assuming air-cooled condensation, during the discharge process, the electric power produced by the ORC amounts to 24.99 MW_e, while during the charge process, the electric power absorbed amounts to 15.09 MW_e. Considering that the gross power of the Kizildere geothermal plant is about 50 MW_e, it is evident that the both ETES electric power production and consumption are relevant with respect to the overall plant electric power: this means that, when the electric energy price is low, running the ETES absorbs a power which implies a net power production of 34.91 MW_e (70% of the full power value); on the other side, when the electric energy price is high, running the ETES allows a supplementary electric power which corresponds to a total power production of 74.99 MW_e (150% of the full value); the resulting RTE amounts to approximately 82.78%. As stated, these values should be considered as limit values, representing the best possible advantage of the ETES application; the techno-economic analysis will then be crucial to assess the economic advantage of the ETES adoption and the optimal size of the system.

Future work will focus on developing an improved simulation model of the SEHRENE ETES, based on the detailed sizing of all the system components, and incorporating the component dynamic behavior. This will enable a more accurate assessment of ETES performance, particularly under charging and discharging conditions that differ from the base case. Coupled with a techno-economic analysis, this approach will be essential for evaluating the profitability of the ETES in the context of fluctuating electricity prices and as possible back-up unit in case of black-out.

NOMENCLATURE

Acronyms

SEHRENE Store Electricity and Heat foR climatE Neutral Europe

ETES Electro-Thermal Energy Storage

TES Thermal Energy Storage

PCM Phase Change Material

ORC Organic Rankine Cycle

HTHP High Temperature Heat Pump

RTE Round Trip Efficiency

Subscripts

e electric

th thermal

REFERENCES

- Alp Sahiller H., Rougé S.. Enhancing the flexibility of electricity generation and heating for Kızıldereli II geothermal power plant by demonstrating heat storage systems. 9th Eur. Conf. Ren. Energy Sys. 21-23 April 2021, Istanbul, Turkey (2021)
- Altieri, R., Bonafin, J., Guercio, M., Bini, R., Bertanzi, R., Belotti, P.: Turboden's ORC grid balancing capability, *Proceedings of the European Geothermal Congress 2016*, Strasbourg, France, (2016), 1-3.
- Irl, M., Aubele, K., Baumann, T., Dawo, F., Hindelang, J., Keim, M., Kuhn, P., Mayer-Ullmann, P., Molar-Cruz, A., Walcher, F., Wieland, C., Eller, T., Heberle F., Flexibilitätsoptionen der Strom- und Wärmezeugung mit Geothermie in einem von volatilem Stromangebot bestimmten Energiesystem. (2020) *Climate Change* 24/2020.
- Cendoya, A., Chaudoir, B., Janod, T., Hazar, T., Halaçoğlu, U., Lemort, V. (2024). Carnot battery integration in a geothermal power plant: study case

of Zorlu Enerji. 1st Belgian Symposium of Thermodynamics, Proceedings (2024)

D'Incalci, M., Alfani, D., Bombarda, P., Preliminary Analysis of an Electro-Thermal Energy Storage System for Geothermal Application; Proceeding ORC 2025, Lappeenranta, Finland (2025)

Merbecks, T., Leal, A., Bombarda, P., Silva, P., Alfani, D., Saar, M., GeoProp: A thermophysical property modelling framework for single and two-phase geothermal geofluids, *Geothermics*, (2025), 125 103146

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action, Grant Agreement^o 101135763.

This study was carried out within the NEST - Network 4 Energy Sustainable Transition (D.D. 1243 02/08/2022, PE00000021) and received funding under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.3, funded from the European Union - NextGenerationEU.

This manuscript reflects only the authors' views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.